

MPowerBIO

eM-POWERing SME Clusters to help SMEs to overcome the valley of death

D6.2 MPowerBIO website

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Bio-based Industries Consortium

www.mpowerbio.eu

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MPOWERBIO PARTNERS				
Participant No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country	Organisation type
1	Food & Bio Cluster Denmark http://foodbiocluster.dk/	FBCD	DK	Non-profit SME/Cluster
2	TechTour Global https://www.techtour.com/	TTG	BG	SME
3	CLIB https://www.clib2021.de/	CLIB	DE	Non-profit SME/Cluster
4	Corporacion Tecnologica de Andalucia https://www.corporaciontecnologica.com/es/	CTA	ES	Non-profit Research Centre/Cluster
5	Italbiotec https://www.italbiotec.it/	IBT	IT	Non-profit Research Centre/Cluster
6	FoodScale Hub https://foodscaleshub.com/	FSH	RS	Non-profit Association /Cluster
7	EIT Food https://www.eitfood.eu/	EIT	BE	Non-profit Association
8	Irish Bioeconomy Foundation https://bioeconomyfoundation.com/	IBF	IE	Non-profit SME/Cluster
9	Q-Plan International https://qplan-intl.gr/	QPL	GR	SME
10	Sustainable Innovations Europe https://www.sustainableinnovations.eu/	SIE	ES	SME

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1. Deliverable Description

For communication and dissemination purposes, a dedicated MPowerBIO website has been developed. The website was launched in M6 and is available at mpowerbio.eu. The website provides information about the project's concepts, main goals, partners involved in the consortium and expected results, showcasing the project's news, progress and acting as a communication channel with clusters, investors and stakeholders.

The website currently includes the following sections:

- **Front page:** Brief summary of the project, the value propositions and overview of services, infographic that explains how the program works.
- **About:** A short description of the project including an infographic showing the timeline of the project, a description of the goals and objectives in the project, partner logos and an overview of the members of the advisory board.
- **Services:** A description of the project's services and the possibility to choose whether you are a cluster or an SME in relation to getting information about the capacity building or business support programme.
- **Contact:** A contact form which is directed at the project manager, Britt Sandvad, Food and Bio Cluster Denmark.

At a later stage the website will also include:

- **Digital tools:** Training materials for use by clusters and cluster SMEs to facilitate the gathering of SMEs profiles, assess their investment readiness level and identify their strengths and weaknesses. In addition, guides will be available for SME clusters on how to help their SMEs
- **Courses:** Information about courses, which is divided into different categories.
- **News:** A news section where relevant information about the MPowerBIO project will be posted, including press releases and articles.
- **Events:** A calendar showing all upcoming events related to the MPowerBIO project. The calendar is divided into different categories, so it is easy to find the type of event you are looking for.
- **Resources:** A download section for all the communication materials as well as project report deliverables.

On the website you can also find a link to MPowerBIO's social media account on LinkedIn.

The website is designed in a responsive design, which means that the layout of the webpage is adjusted and adapted to any screen size, whether you are using for example your phone or a tablet.

Figure 1 Front page part one

Figure 2 Front page part two

Why participate

SMEs

- Get tools to enhance your investment readiness
- Get in touch with investors regionally and internationally
- Get concrete advice on your business strategy and pitch

Clusters

- Be better equipped to help your SME members become ready for investment
- You can add a new service to your portfolio which your members can benefit from – or improve the existing service
- Upgrade the skills of your secretariat

Investors

- Get in touch with SMEs that can present attractive business plans ready for investment
- One point of entry to over 250 SMEs with high-growth potential within the bio-based industry
- Get a "greener" investment profile

How does it work?

1. Training Modules for Clusters

To enhance the investment readiness of SMEs, MPowerBIO will offer training modules for clusters to be better equipped to help their SMEs.

2. Tools and Training Activities for SMEs

SMEs will be offered concrete tools through this online platform and through training activities which will improve their investment readiness and pitching skills.

3. Connect SMEs with Investors

MPowerBIO will connect SMEs with investors by organising regional and international events where SMEs have the opportunity to pitch their business proposition and network with the audience.

APPLY NOW

Figure 3 Front page part three

Key services

Capacity building programme

Increase your success rate in helping your SME members gain access to funding. The capacity building programme is designed to support you in assessing the challenges of gaining access to funding and to be able to deliver better advice and services for your SME members.

[Read More](#)

Business support programme

Let's make your business ready for investment. Identify your challenges and weaknesses and receive tailored support to improve your chances to capture investments for your bio-based industry projects. Discover how we can help you and your business succeed.

[Read More](#)

Events

Participate in free regional training events and EU wide networking events to boost your investment readiness and growth potential and connect with investors and potential partners.

[Read More](#)

Figure 4 Front page part four

Partners

Get in touch

We'd love to have your feedback and answer your questions

[Contact us](#)

[Privacy & Cookies Policy](#) [Terms and Conditions](#) [Contact](#)

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Figure 5 About page

MPowerBIO About Services Contact [Apply Now](#)

Home > About

About

MPowerBIO empowers Clusters to bring SMEs across the financial valley of death

Many SMEs experience that even though they have a good idea or a good product, they cannot get an investor. They need to be able to pitch their idea perfectly, have a strong business plan, a clear strategy, a well-defined customer base, etc. to attract investors.

European clusters need to be better suited to help small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) overcome the valley of death i.e. the difficult task of finding sufficient investment to get from idea to business. This is the main focus of the MPowerBIO project.

In the MPowerBIO project 10 training the trainers' events will be arranged for a total of 90 clusters across the bioeconomy, covering most of Europe. The events are set up to help clusters understand how SMEs can obtain capital and grow.

Our goals and objectives

10 training the trainers events	90 clusters	250 SMEs	10 regional competitions	2 European final pitching events
The events are set up to help clusters to be better equipped to help SMEs overcome the challenge of finding sufficient investment	The project will engage and train 90 SME clusters within the bio-based industry across Europe	The SMEs will be screened and supported over the project to enhance their investment readiness level	SMEs will present high-quality bio-based industry projects to investors at regional competitions	The best SME projects will be invited to pitch at one of the annual European final events

How will we reach the goals?

01 Identify investment challenges

The MPowerBIO project will obtain feedback from clusters, SMEs and investors on the concrete challenges they have regarding investments. From these experiences, an online platform will be set up containing digital tools for evaluating investment readiness.

02 Train clusters and support SMEs

Online training modules and regional trainers' events will be organised to build the capacity of clusters to train their SME members and give them the best possibilities for preparing and presenting high quality projects to investors.

03 Pitching in front of investors

The best SME projects from these events will be selected by investors, and invited to one of two European finals, which are based on the European Bioeconomy Venture Forum model, run by several of the consortium members. At the final, the selected companies will present their ideas to a panel of investors and experts from large organisations and venture funds in Europe, with the aim of attracting capital to grow and develop their business. A total of 72 high-quality, screened and investment-ready SME are expected to pitch at the two final events. The project will screen and support 250 SMEs towards this goal.

Figure 6 Services page

Services

Whether you are a SME or a cluster, we offer a set of tailored services that have been carefully selected to meet your needs in relation to improving your investment readiness for your bio-based industry projects. Click below to discover how we can help you succeed.

I am

SME Cluster

Services for SMEs

Business support programme

Ready to be ready? The Business Support Program includes services selected to meet the needs of the participants such as:

Pitching competitions

SMEs will present their projects to selected investors for a place in one of the European final events.

[Read More](#)

E-learning

Through our e-learning platform, SMEs will be offered online courses and training materials.

[Read More](#)

Coaching

Coaches will guide SMEs along their way to improve their investment readiness potential.

[Read More](#)

Bioeconomy Bootcamps

Bootcamps tailored to the needs of SMEs will help them boost their skills.

[Read More](#)

How do we do it?

01 Self-assessment

Each interested SME will fill in a profile and fill in a customised self-assessment questionnaire that helps assessing its investment readiness.

02 Assessment by clusters

Following the self-assessment made by the SME itself, an assessment will be done by the associated cluster to which the SME is related, and another assessment will be made by a second cluster (or an appointed expert)

03 Action plan

Finally, the two clusters will define together with the SME, based on the three assessments, an action plan with services to be taken by the SME to improve its investor readiness.

Figure 7 Contact page

Home > Contact

Contact

First Name

Last Name

Organization name

Email Address

Message related to:
- Select -

Message

Send message

Britt Sandvad
Project coordinator
+45 2040 9679
bs@foodbiocluster.dk

2. How the deliverable relates to the objectives of WP6

The website play an important role in relation to several of the objectives in WP6. Firstly, the main objective, which is to maximise the impact and the dissemination of the project and its results to multiple audiences. Through the website the project delivers targeted information to multiple audiences. Secondly, the website will contribute and support the objective of increasing relevant stakeholders' awareness of the existence and importance of the project, its ultimate results, innovative processes and new products. Thirdly the website relates to the goal of ensuring proper knowledge exchange and activities by sharing news and deliverables, promoting events and courses and by making training materials and guides available through the digital tools section.